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Temperature resistance of epoxy-based polymer coating with fly ash and fire retardant fillers for composite materials

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INTRODUCTION

Applications of epoxy based polymers

- Bonding of structural elements
- Infill for structural repair systems
- Coating for railway sleepers

Bonding of structural elements
(www.usa.sika.com)

Pipe exterior repair: filling defect with wrapping epoxy wetted carbon fabric around the defect (Duell et al. 2008)

Composite sleeper made of sandwich panels coated by epoxy polymer matrix
(Ferdous & Manalo, 2016)

Background

Storage modulus curve neat epoxy and its nanocomposites (Wan et al., 2014)

Flexural stress-strain behaviours (Ferdous et al., 2016)

Compressive stress-strain behaviours (Lokuge and Aravinthan, 2013)

Methodology

The materials employed in this investigation are an epoxy resin and its hardener, and light-weight fillers.

- DGEBA* based epoxy resin (Part-A)
- Amine based curing agent (Part-B)
- Fire retardant (FRF)
- Fly ash (FA)

Left to right: Part-A, Part-B, FRF and FA

Sample preparation

Methodology

Properties	Tests	Parameters
Thermo-mechanical	DMA* (ASTM D7028)	Filler (%) (0, 20, 40, 60)
Mechanical	Compression (ASTM C579)	
	Split Tensile (ASTM C579)	Temperature (°C) (RT, 40, 50, 60, 80)
Microstructure	SEM** FTIR***	

a) Compressive Strength

b) Split Tensile

c) DMA

Results and discussion

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA)

Hard Glassy

Soft Rubbery

a) storage modulus vs temperature

b) Tan delta vs temperature

Variations in dynamic mechanical properties vs temperature

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Results and discussion

RT

40°C and 50°C

60°C and 80°C

(a) F0 (b) F20 (c) F40 (d) F60

Failures mode

Compressive Strength

Stress vs Strain behaviour of F0

Stress vs Strain behaviour of F60

Compressive strength retention at in-service elevated temperature

Results and discussion

RT

40°C and 50°C

60°C and 80°C

(a) F0 (b) F20 (c) F40 (d) F60

Failures observed after split tensile

Split Tensile strength

Stress vs Strain behaviour of F0

Stress vs Strain behaviour of F60

Splitting tensile strength retention at in-service elevated temperature

a) RT

b) 80°C

SEM micrographs of F60 at room temperature and 80°C

Results and discussion

FTIR

a) F0

b) F60

FTIR graphs at room temperature and 80°C

Conclusions

- Adding up to 60% of filler to the polymer matrix increased the T_g by at least 5°C from 57°C to 62°C
- Large increase in ductility (strain to failure) and reduction in ultimate strength were observed at elevated temperatures. Nevertheless, the addition of fillers led to retention of compressive and tensile strengths by up to 72% and 52%, respectively for F60 at the maximum test temperature of 80°C
- SEM images showed the formation of dense microstructure with utilizing fillers in the mixtures at high temperatures. This resulted in higher compressive and split tensile strength retention in epoxy with fillers under elevated temperature.
- FTIR analysis indicated that C-H and C-O were found to be major phases for all specimens. All of the functional groups mixes had the same peak values at their lowest and highest temperatures except shifting of band by increasing of temperature, which shows in-service temperature did not lead to significant changes in the spectra of different mixes.

THANK YOU ...

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